

CHALLENGES TO THE HIGHER EDUCATION TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

New challenges in the field of digital transformation and content conveyed in the education process, in particular engineering sciences, triggered a discussion on the identification of issues focused on forms of cooperation with recipients using the available tools and taking into account the individual predispositions and knowledge of students related to their soft and hard competences. The subject of the paper is an attempt to identify students' soft competences on the basis of observations during the digital transformation period in 2020-2021.

Technology has a significant impact on education, but also human and social factors have a significant impact on shaping the new future of universities, especially those with an engineering profile. The experience of the last 2 years shows the need for an integrated approach to the education process, which should take into account the content provided in combination with a properly selected form of cooperation with recipients using the available tools and taking into account the individual predispositions and knowledge of students (attention should be paid to the so-called soft and hard skills).

1 INTRODUCTION

Educational processes, in particular in the field of engineering sciences, are clearly associated with the digital transformation in the life of societies on a global scale, as well as with changes taking place in industry and broadly understood business. An important document indicating the occurrence of various types of changes in the world and the need for systemic action is included in the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDG, 2015).

Digital transformation is the result of a combination of information, communication and artificial intelligence, which is associated with transformation in thinking and acting, as well as interoperability and a transdisciplinary approach to perceiving and solving engineering problems. In (Guerdier et al, 2022), the authors state that the skills of students and educators in the learning process are key. There is a shift away from classical skills (reading, writing, arithmetic) to new skills and competences focused on big data (data mining, sharing, modeling) and related to critical creative thinking and the possibility of human interaction with intelligent machines. Moreover, it has been found that students are currently able to obtain specific knowledge from sources other than traditional forms of communication at the university and are able to pass the exams of the course without having to attend formal classes.

In the paper (Guerdier et al, 2020) it was stated that the currently developed cyber-physical systems (CPS, Cyber Physical Systems) are a significant challenge for the education process with an engineering profile. It was found that solutions aimed at a different form of delivered content should be sought in connection with the interdisciplinary integration of data and data labels with digital programs and educational methodologies, taking into account the need for quick adaptation to changing working conditions.

The paper (Doyle-Kent & Watson, 2021) proposes the idea of a global engineer type who works in an international socially diverse environment requiring hard (technical) and soft (non-technical) skills. Related to these challenges are the need for lifelong learning, in particular the need to learn in real work environments.

The paper (Pursula et al., 2005) presents the concept of the development of virtual universities in Europe. It was found, inter alia, that with virtual teaching, new pedagogical issues will be released, as the work environment will be significantly different from that to which lecturers and students are used to.

In the paper (Miranda et al, 2021), the authors formulate conclusions regarding the challenges for the engineering education process in the period of digital transformation. The conclusions concern the development of: competences (especially critical), new learning methods, digital tools (information and communication technologies), infrastructure for education.

Technology has a significant impact on education, but also human and social factors have a significant impact on shaping the new future of universities, especially those with an engineering profile. New challenges in the field of digital transformation in the field of content conveyed in the education process, in particular engineering

sciences, triggered a discussion on the identification of issues focused on forms of cooperation with recipients (students) with the use of available tools and taking into account the individual predispositions and knowledge of students related to their soft skills and hard. The subject of the paper is an attempt to identify students' soft competences on the basis of observations during the digital transformation period in 2020-2021.

The paper presents the observations of the effects of introducing a new learning environment (digital, and earlier learning process and achievements) in connection with the psychophysical properties of the student and the acquisition of knowledge and good practices in the new complex reality. Formulating the methodology of education in the new reality is not an easy issue and constitutes a significant challenge for educators in connection with new business models. Development of the presented issues is planned in the future.

2 OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

The global pandemic situation forced in 2020 a rapid digital transformation of educators and the available infrastructure for the education process of students. An additional effect of the situation that has arisen is the discussion on a new approach to education processes perceived jointly in relation to: the addressee (the resources of available knowledge, competences and skills, their health and mental state, educational susceptibility and motivation), evolutionary changes in the labor market in a global system and anticipated needs in terms of the competences and skills of employees and academic teachers (resources of substantive knowledge, competences and skills, health and mental condition, knowledge and practice in the field of methods and tools useful in the education process, motivation). This paper presents observations and conclusions from the period of rapid transformation of the process of training engineers from traditional (in-presence) to remote digital (on-line).

The following research issues were identified::

1. strengths and weaknesses of remote or mixed learning (limitations in the implementation of practical and blackboard classes, targeted debates, consultations, distribution of educational materials, lecture formula);
2. methods of activating students to the learning process, ways of becoming interested in a specific topic of classes;
3. selecting appropriate methods for conveying the educational content;
4. digital techniques in the education process and digital competences of the teacher and student;
5. planning classes / training;
6. the essence of the pedagogical approach to students in the education process;
7. personality characteristics of students and educators;
8. loneliness of the educator and participant of didactic classes / training;
9. fatigue and burnout of partners in the education process;

It was noticed that the formula of webinars and online meetings allowed for the construction of a new space for conveying specific content, and also for group

debates focused on good practices in the education process, getting to know meeting participants, the possibility of being listened to and positively motivated to act. The formula of debating and educating with the use of digital techniques was the expected solution after a long period of physical isolation of the participants of the education process and a specific form of social therapy.

A new digital community of academic teachers and students was created, who together began to discover new issues (phenomena, areas for development) important in the process of education and professional work. For example:

1. difficulties in reading and listening to the transmitted content with comprehension and assimilation. The expectations of students in terms of special substantive care, targeted counseling and shaping and supporting the process of making targeted decisions are observed.
2. personal competences of the educator and student expressed, among others, by: self-awareness (recognizing emotions, self-esteem), self-management (stress, coping with stress, self-motivation and self-discipline), building relationships with the listener (communication, conflict resolution), empathy (emotional type: the ability to feel other people's mental states, cognitive type: the ability to adopt the way of thinking and perceiving reality by other people), assertiveness (having and expressing one's own opinion without aggressive behavior while maintaining good social habits), the ability to make decisions (problem solving, analytical thinking, responsibility).
3. methods of activating educators and students to the learning process, building a relationship between the student and the teacher, appreciating the pedagogical aspects of the teaching process, intergenerational communication.
4. storytelling in education. Building a specific targeted plot around the product / technical object (object, operation, functions, power supply, disturbances) using the commitment and emotions of the recipients (students) and their positive associations or creating specific needs among them.
5. procrastination in education. Voluntary, deliberate delay in carrying out the intended actions resulting in a short-term improvement in well-being, followed by time stress in connection with the ability to accurately and correctly perform the planned activity. Emotions and impulsiveness (including the desire to obtain immediate reward) negatively affect the concentration and own management of the perception and time senses (the consequence is postponement of the task and possible negative emotions). Depressive and dysthymic disorders as well as anxiety disorders associated with possible failure (expressed inability) are observed, which lead to frustration (specific protection of self-esteem), passive-aggressive behavior and the phenomenon of professional burnout.
6. living under stress and seeking strong sensations resulting in the illusory awareness of mobilization to meet a difficult challenge with perfect implementation.
7. anxiety about failure or success, helplessness or isolation and intimacy.

8. digital wellbeing in education (digital wellness). Digital well-being of lecturers and students who implement the educational process, related to the promotion of maintaining their healthy lifestyle with the use of available digital technologies. Example of negative impact of digital technologies: abuse of social media, educator and student productivity (maintaining the balance between work / education and private life).

The presented selected issues require the development of solutions (methods and tools), and then the formulation of a methodology for transferring knowledge and practice in a systemic manner that fits into the current and future business requirements.

The paper has a reflective character in which digital and soft student skills are analyzed.

Today's reality forces us to look for teachers who teach new advanced technological systems. In particular, trainers who teach how to code human behavior, clarifiers that link technology and practice, leaders who can explain the technology used, supervisors who maintain advanced twin systems oriented towards sustainable development in practice.

Education changes people and infrastructure, ensures people's well-being and is a source of intellectual and economic development. A systemic approach to education and safe human activities in a specific environment is related to sustainable development. Education for sustainable development should be a source of knowledge and conscious human action focused on the individual and community, prepare young people for the ability to undertake transformational activities for sustainable development

3 SUMMARY

Education never ends. The experience of the last 2 years indicates the need for an integrated approach to the education process, which should take into account the content provided in combination with a properly selected form of cooperation with recipients using available tools and taking into account the individual predispositions and knowledge of students (pay attention jointly to the so-called soft and hard competences). The proposed systemic approach to the issue is in line with the United Nations 2030 Agenda (in particular, goal 4: good quality of education) in terms of promoting a sustainable lifestyle and educating about sustainable development throughout life. The cooperation between educators inside and outside the university is easier, their joint purposeful mobilization is easier. The learning paradigm and teaching methods require improvement with a focus on digital transformation of educators and infrastructure in the process of educating students. New digital technologies should also be taken into account, for example: mobile computing, the Internet of everything combined with machine learning.

Engineers with specific knowledge and competences are key in achieving the sustainable development goals set out in the 2030 Agenda. New integrated technical, social, environmental and economic challenges are formulated before the engineering staff. Meeting the new challenge is possible as a result of implementing holistic engineering education combined with innovations oriented towards sustainable development. The consequence is the need to build engineering programs that inspire creativity and new creative thinking.

With the process of technological development, the society and its successive generations are also changing as they interact with the Internet and its services and, to a certain extent, autonomously. Noticeable psychophysical changes in society translate into the need to pay attention to the so-called soft skills of students and lecturers, which require improvement. The article attempts to identify students' soft competences on the basis of observations during the digital transformation period in 2020-2021 that require inclusion in shaping hard competences. Moreover, attention was drawn to the necessity of lifelong learning with the use of available resources as well as digital tools and methods, a transdisciplinary approach to the educational process, and the improvement of human-technology-environment interactions.

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